

Implementing a National System of Grant Identifiers in India's Funding Agencies

Summary

Tracking research outputs and outcomes from publicly funded projects remains a challenge in India due to the absence of standardized, persistent identifiers for grants. This policy brief proposes the adoption of a **national system of grant identifiers** by Indian public funding agencies to improve recognition of funded research, enhance transparency, and enable robust impact assessment. A unique grant identifier, linked to researchers, institutions, and outputs, will facilitate accurate attribution, reduce administrative inefficiencies, and integrate Indian research into global open science infrastructure. Drawing on international best practices, the brief outlines implementation strategies, governance considerations, and potential benefits for policymakers, funding bodies, and the research community. The proposed system aims to strengthen accountability, visibility, and long-term evaluation of India's research investments.

Introduction

Research publications (especially journal articles) serve as key indicators for assessing the impact of research funding programs, the performance of funding agencies, and the overall performance of the research ecosystem. An accurate acknowledgment of funding sources in publications not only recognizes the financial support but also aids in tracking the outcomes associated with specific funding programs and the projects that are funded through them.

Figure 1. Percentage of research articles acknowledging all funding agencies (both public and private) across different countries in the period 2014-2018 and 2019-2023.

The plot in Figure 1 (produced using data reported in a recent study [1]) displays the percentage of papers from four selected countries that mention a funding source in their acknowledgement section; for convenience, we have selected the two most recent five-year periods: 2014-18 and 2019-23. It is clear that the fraction of papers from China, the USA, and the UK with acknowledgement of funding sources is higher than that of papers from India by a factor of two or more. This is all the more striking since it is understood that S&T research in India's research and higher education institutions is driven predominantly by funding from government agencies such as DST, DBT, and ANRF (formerly SERB).

With the rise of digital technologies and use of web crawlers by indexing bodies (such as Web of Science, Scopus, Dimensions, etc), details from acknowledgements section in journal articles are being acquired with greater ease and accuracy; this information is also easily accessible to the funding bodies and can help in policy formulation (or fine-tuning) as well as in assessing the efficacy and impact of their funding programs. It is important to ensure that Indian researchers provide an adequate and accurate acknowledgement to their funding sources in their papers.

Current Scenario

In the following examples, we provide multiple ways in which funding acknowledgements are written. For convenience, we choose DST as the funding body in these examples.

1. Generic/overbroad acknowledgements: It is common to find a generic acknowledgement to "Department of Science and Technology, Government of India" without mentioning the specific program through which funding was obtained.
2. Non-standard acknowledgements: "Department of Science and Technology, Government of India" may be written in multiple forms: DST, Dept. S&T, Dept. Sci. Tech., DST-Gol, etc. This makes disambiguation difficult in the sense that the WoS may identify each as a distinct entity.
3. Acknowledgement with an identifier associated with the researchers' institution. For example, researchers from the Indian Institute of Science may acknowledge funding from the Department of Science and Technology through the project "SP/DSTO-1352"; However, this identifier -- "SP/DSTO-1352" -- is meaningful only within the context of IISc since it is used for managing the funds within the IISc portal for financial administration!

Problems in the current unstructured approach

The current practice of using a generic and/or non-standard wording in the acknowledgements section is clearly undesirable since:

- It poses a major challenge for funding agencies and institutions to accurately track the research outputs stemming from project grants under various programs.
- It also hampers the ability to measure the impact of funded projects, affecting future funding decisions and policy formulations.
- It diminishes the visibility and perceived value of funding agencies' contributions to scientific advancement.

Solution: Grant Identifiers

In this policy brief, we recommend that the Department of Science and Technology lead a national initiative (involving all the government funding agencies) to create and implement a system of Grant Identifiers (GI), along with a mandate to all researchers that the acknowledgement in their research papers and reports (and other written output) must report the GI (through which they received the grant) clearly and unambiguously; some suggestions are given below. Such a system can address these problems directly and effectively. The key advantages include:

1. Enhanced Traceability: Grant Identifiers allow for precise linkage between research publications and their corresponding funded projects. This facilitates easier tracking of research outcomes, publications, patents, and other outputs associated with each project.
2. Such a standardized system of Grant Identifiers ensures uniform acknowledgement across publications, reducing ambiguity and improving data quality in bibliometric analyses.
3. With Grant Identifiers, funding agencies can systematically evaluate the impact and productivity of their funded projects, enabling data-driven decision-making.
4. Clear attribution of research outputs to specific projects enhances transparency and accountability, encouraging responsible research practices.
5. Consistent acknowledgement through Grant Identifiers increases the visibility of funding agencies' contributions to the scientific progress of the nation, fostering trust and continued support.

International comparison

We find that this practice of using a specific Grant Identifier (or Number or Code) is being practiced widely by researchers from several leading countries. In the United States, for example, the National Science Foundation [2] mandates that "... the recipient is responsible for assuring that an acknowledgment of NSF support is made" and recommends the use of specific wording: "This material is based upon work supported by the National Science Foundation under Award No. (NSF award number)." Similarly, guidelines from the National Institutes of Health [3] mandate a "specific acknowledgment of NIH grant support" that includes the phrase "the National Institutes of Health" the "award number [specific NIH grant number(s) in this format: R01GM987654]."

In the following, we mention several similar examples we found in recent papers from several other countries; in their acknowledgements section, they mention both the funding agency's name in full (i.e., without abbreviation) and the specific grant (using a Grant Identifier / Number / Code) through which funding was received.

JAPAN:

Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology, Japan (MEXT)

Japan Society for the Promotion of Science Grants-in-Aid for Scientific Research (KAKENHI)

Grant No: 20H00633

CHINA

Key Research Program of Frontier Sciences, Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS)

Grant No: QYZDJ-SSW-SLH011

SOUTH KOREA

National Research Foundation of Korea

Grant No: 2016R1-D1A1B-01010135

AUSTRALIA

Australian Research Council

Grant No: DP180102629

Policy Recommendations

[i] It is recommended that each funding body (such as DST, DBT, CSIR, ANRF, ...) implement a Grant Identifier for each project that is funded by it.

In order to maximize the benefits, we recommend that the naming convention allow for embedding as much information as possible without it making the identifier unwieldy. We suggest a Grant Identifier in the following format:

**[COUNTRY]-[FUNDING-AGENCY]-[YEAR]-[PROGRAMCODE]-
[SERIALNUMBER]'**

For a DST grant made in 2022, for example, it would look like this: IN-DST-22-004-1023, where "004" maps to a program within DST and "1023" maps to the specific project that received the grant under this program.

This has the advantage that anyone would be able to identify the country, funding agency, and the year of the grant. For policy makers (within DST, for example), however, this convention provides richer, more detailed information at the program level, and through reverse mapping, specific sub-program under which the grant was made.

[ii] It is further recommended that each funding body include a mandate to grant recipients to incorporate the specific wording in the acknowledgements section of any written output (journal articles, web articles, reports, patent-related documents, etc) that arises from the work supported by the grant. An example:

"The author(s) acknowledge the financial support for this work from the Department of Science and Technology, Government of India, through the grant [Grant Identifier]."

While other variations are possible, the wording in all such variations should preferably include the phrases “Department of Science and Technology, Government of India” (in full, without abbreviation or any other modification) and “[Grant Identifier]”.

[iii] It is recommended that DST’s portal for managing projects include a separate section in the page where grant recipients submit their annual or final report(s); in this section they are asked to provide the details of the papers arising out of the work supported by the grant, as well as an assurance from the grant recipient(s) that they have complied with the mandate for the acknowledgements section.

Implementation

An effective implementation of this system of Grant Identifiers will require several key steps, including:

- Developing a nationwide registry to assign, manage, and link the project details.
- Engaging with the grant applicants to alert them about the above mandate for the acknowledgements section; these engagements may be through periodic emails, social media posts, project appraisal and review meetings, and periodic workshops.
- Regular assessment of the effectiveness of the system and refine procedures as needed.

Conclusion

An effective implementation of this system of Grant Identifiers will require several key steps, including:

- Developing a nationwide registry to assign, manage, and link the project details.
- Engaging with the grant applicants to alert them about the above mandate for the acknowledgements section; these engagements may be through periodic emails, social media posts, project appraisal and review meetings, and periodic workshops.
- Regular assessment of the effectiveness of the system and refine procedures as needed.

References

- [1] Scientometric Analysis of India's Academic Progress in the Period 2014-2023 (under revision) to be submitted to the Department of Science and Technology, Government of India (2025).
- [2] Proposal & Award Policies and Procedures Guide, National Science Foundation (NSF), USA.
- [3] Communicating and Acknowledging Federal Funding, National Institutes of Health (NIH), USA